

MAPPING COVID-19 VACCINATION UPTAKE IN REGION XII

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic is one of the biggest problems that the world has faced in recent years, and it highlights our vulnerability to infections. The implementation of vaccines was one solution to combat this pandemic; however, a variety of different vaccine brands led to vaccine hesitancy and the inability to achieve herd immunity, limiting the impact of vaccination. This study evaluates and assesses the implications of the current administration of vaccine dose in Region XII, focusing on the total vaccine dose obtained from the Department of Health - Resbakuna. This study used Tableau and GeoGebra to derive the study's main results. The results show that 56.84% of the population of Region XII is fully vaccinated, which implies vaccine hesitancy. The results also reveal that Pfizer is the most administered vaccine in Region XII. Additionally, differences in vaccine doses among areas suggest unequal distribution, possibly due to vaccine availability, population density, and hesitancy toward certain brands. Hence, limited access to certain vaccine brands in different areas results in some areas having more people vaccinated with specific brands. Moreover, it is recommended that the government use the vaccine administration data to create specific policies, improve transparency for residents, and help medical professionals enhance vaccination strategies.

Keywords: *COVID-19, Vaccinations, Hesitancy, Vaccine brands*

INTRODUCTION

The SARS-CoV-2 virus brought about the harmful COVID-19 pandemic, leading the World Health Organization to classify it as a global pandemic (Buheji et al., 2020). The Philippine government employed non-pharmaceutical interventions in hopes of fighting against the pandemic. The significant increase in reported active cases resulted in the government imposing measures to ease and prevent the further spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. These interventions include lockdowns, curfews, and limitations in social gatherings (Jiang et al., 2022).

One measure imposed by the government to prevent further spread of the disease is vaccination. Vaccination is one of the most effective ways to reduce the severity of infectious diseases. A study by Cababan et al. (2021) stated that the community should become more responsive and take positive action on the COVID-19 vaccination action plan. The study by Paltiel et al. (2021) also stated that health officials must invest more financial support in vaccine production and distribution to combat the COVID-19 pandemic effectively, and public health authorities must grasp which demographic is more inclined toward vaccine admissions or hesitancy.

According to Statista (2023), over 13 billion COVID-19 vaccine doses have been administered worldwide, and the Philippines has already issued a total of 166,058,133 doses in January 2023 (COVID-19 Tracker | Department of Health, 2023). The country has approved and administered a total of 7 different vaccine brands, namely Pfizer, Moderna, AstraZeneca, Janssen, Sinopharm, Sputnik V, and Sinovac, most of which have been used throughout the other regions of the Philippines (Cababan et al., 2021). Visualizations were created to determine provincial and municipal patterns within Region XII using available secondary data on vaccine administration.

Misinformation on vaccine administration may lead to vaccine hesitancy, which inhibits effective vaccine implementation within the region. According to a study conducted by Wang et al. (2022), a variety of factors may influence vaccination uptake, possibly affected by vaccination acceptance where individuals have different conspiracy beliefs, vaccine confidence, and other psychological factors. A comprehensive understanding of these factors and their impact on vaccination uptake paves the way for future researchers to study prospects that may affect the administration trend. For this reason, this study examined the COVID-19 vaccination data through a region-wide mapping assessment of Region XII. The study determined the association between vaccine brands and geographic areas through the test of independence.

Research Questions

This research assesses and evaluates the administration of vaccine dose in Region XII, the brand of vaccine, and the total number of vaccination dose per area in Region XII.

Specifically, it aims to determine the vaccination dosage per brand of vaccine by area. This study includes the percentage of fully vaccinated individuals, assesses the

association between the brand of vaccine dosage and area, and evaluates the impact of the COVID-19 vaccines on current COVID-19 cases.

1. What is the current vaccination situation in Region XII?
2. How do demographics such as geographic area associate with different vaccine brands?

METHODOLOGY

The study used secondary data from the official website of the Department of Health - Resbakuna, specifically from the SOCCSKSARGEN Region chapter (Region Vaccination Dashboard, 2023). It includes the total number of vaccinations for each vaccine brand from each province in Region XII: South Cotabato, North Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, and Sarangani. Additionally, each province's spatial data, population, and respective municipalities were collected for data visualization.

Data visualization graphically portrays data to make it more appealing and understandable to viewers. It effectively draws attention to the most valuable findings in a set of information and makes it less challenging to identify associations, trends, anomalies, and patterns (Stevens, 2021). Tableau Public Software generated heatmaps and bubble plots to incorporate appropriate data visualization.

The chi-square test of independence analyzes the relationship between dichotomous independent variables and offers a quantitative basis for interpreting the findings (McHugh, 2013; Turney, 2022). Geogebra was used as the software for the association test. The variables of interest in this study pertained to the geographical area where the vaccine brands were administered. The probability setting was used to obtain the chi-square statistic of the data analysis.

RESULTS

Provinces	Population	Fully Vaccinated	%Vaccinated
North Cotabato	1 490 618	840 323	56.37%
Sarangani	558 946	298 839	53.46%
South Cotabato	1 672 791	1 005 116	60.09%
Sultan Kudarat	854 052	456 979	53.51%
Total	4 576 407	2 601 257	56.84%

Table 1. *Distribution of Fully Vaccinated by Provinces, January 2023*

Variables	χ^2	p-value	Remarks
Area vs. vaccines	108 196.38	0.00	Highly Associated

Table 2. Association of Area and Vaccines

Figure 1. Distribution of Vaccine Administrations in Region XII, by Province, 2023

Figure 2. Distribution of Vaccine Administrations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 3. Distribution of Pfizer Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 4. Distribution of Sputnik V Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 5. Distribution of Sinopharm Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 6. Distribution of AstraZeneca Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 7. Distribution of Moderna Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 8. Distribution of Janssen Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023

Figure 9. *Distribution of Sinovac Vaccinations in Region XII, by Municipality, 2023*

DISCUSSION

The results reveal significant variations in the number of administered vaccine brands associated with their geographic area in Region XII. These differences may have resulted from many factors affecting vaccine administration, causing specific locations to have more, fewer, or no administration for particular vaccine brands. The findings reveal a specific trend regarding the municipalities with the highest vaccine administrations; however, the same trend does not exist for the lowest number of administrations in a particular municipality.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), South Cotabato is the most populous province, followed by North Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, and Sarangani, with General Santos City being the most populated city in Region XII and Antipas being the least populated. This information may suggest the possible factor that highly populated areas, such as General Santos City, have high vaccination rates, while in contrast, less populated locations like Antipas and other municipalities have few or no vaccinations for certain vaccine brands. General Santos City was one of the focused locations for the initial rollout of the COVID-19 vaccinations because of the country's high two-week growth rate of infection (Tomacruz, 2020), implying that it may provide evidence of vaccination prioritization since South Cotabato had higher vaccinations than other provinces, while Sarangani had the least.

Additionally, vaccines such as AstraZeneca, Moderna, and Sinovac had South Cotabato and General Santos City as their most vaccinated area; however, Janssen had North Cotabato with General Santos City as their most vaccinated area. The results also show that specific municipalities had little to no vaccination for specific vaccine brands. Sinopharm vaccinations were only present in North Cotabato. At the same time, Sputnik V had vaccinations present only in the following municipalities: Tacurong, M'lang, Kidapawan, General Santos City, Maitum, Makilala, and Matalam, which may indicate

that some vaccines are not available at the location's vaccination sites.

Vaccine hesitancy, influenced by individual beliefs and social factors, may have contributed to low uptake rates in specific locations (Amit et al., 2022). When individuals are reluctant to receive a specific vaccine brand or all vaccines, this hesitancy may reduce the overall vaccination rate; therefore, addressing these concerns through strategic communication is crucial for promoting vaccination (Atinga et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2020). Studies have also shown how vaccine hesitancy is still evident within countries (The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2021). It is also evident that vaccine hesitancy, especially in the Philippines, is significantly higher as compared to other countries, where Filipino participants exhibited a much higher level of COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy compared to Malaysian participants (Brackstone et al., 2022; Cho et al., 2021).

Documentation in tracking dual-dose vaccine administrations and supporting culturally sensitive and evidence-based communication may increase vaccine acceptance (Paltiel et al., 2021). It is also recommended that vaccine confidence be improved through rigorous research to understand the psychological, social, and political factors affecting public trust in vaccines within the region (Larson et al., 2011). Thus, providing more vaccine administration information may help improve vaccine confidence by increasing regional transparency. Furthermore, determining which demographics to consider when purchasing vaccines may help policymakers propose specific policies, maximizing the practical implementation of COVID-19 vaccines.

Conclusions

The study reveals that in January 2023, Region XII did not achieve the threshold values for herd immunity, with 56.84% showing vaccine hesitancy. Pfizer was the most commonly administered vaccine in Region XII compared to other vaccines, as indicated by the results of the presented heat maps of the administration of the vaccines. Pfizer is more commonly administered than other vaccine brands in the region. The province with the highest Pfizer vaccinations is South Cotabato, with General Santos City in terms of municipality.

The chi-square test also revealed a direct association between the brand of vaccines concerning the area of vaccine recipients, indicating that vaccine administration across different areas may not have been distributed equally, influenced by factors such as population density, vaccine brand hesitancy, and vaccine availability in each area. This information suggests that various considerations should be taken when purchasing different vaccine brands to guarantee that COVID-19 vaccinations are implemented effectively. Determining the factors that affect specific areas can benefit the Philippines' economy in successfully allocating vaccines.

Recommendations

The study recommends that other studies consider different regions of the Philippines in determining the vaccine distribution further to discuss the administration dynamics of the COVID-19 vaccines. Observing critical prospects in vaccine administration may provide additional insights into understanding administration dynamics and maximize the implementation of the COVID-19 vaccine administration and, possibly, in future epidemics. Potential policies centered on specific issues faced by the government in administration can be supported and included in other studies. It is also recommended that the government use the vaccine administration data to improve transparency for residents and help medical professionals enhance vaccination strategies.

Recommendations for using software for further studies allow for more accessible analysis and interpretation of data. GeoGebra proved to be an effective method for conducting the chi-square test of independence for the different values of area and type of vaccines. Lastly, Tableau Software offered a quicker and easier way to generate the heat maps included in this study - it is also the most recommended analytics platform for analyzing vast volumes of data. Additionally, it is advisable to use other software applications for specific tasks, as there are limitations to free software options.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Strict adherence to ethical guidelines was followed during the study. Data regarding the number of vaccinations for each vaccine brand for every area was collected from the Department of Health - Resbakuna, the COVID-19 cases data came from the DOH website, and the regional population was collected from the PSA. Although human participation was not directly involved, measures were taken to ensure data privacy. Proper permissions were secured for data access, and transparency was maintained regarding sources and limitations.

The research was conducted with integrity, avoiding conflicts of interest and ensuring objective analysis. Adherence to institutional and regulatory guidelines was upheld, and ethical considerations were integrated into data analysis. The broader implications for public health and policy were carefully considered. These efforts ensure that the research contributes valuable insights while upholding ethical standards.

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